

Authentication in Mobile Adhoc Network using Neural Network

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Abstract—Mobile adhoc networks paves the way for ubiquitous computing. Mobile adhoc networks is widely used in all the instant communications due to the easier deployment and availability of resources in reasonable cost.Since any nodes can easily join the network, security in mobile adhoc network is highly concentrated in all the applications.Authentication schemes is one of the first initial step to be carried out to prevent malicious node from entering and accessing the network.Several authentication procedures are used which may increase the computational overhead.In this paper,authentication is performed using Neural Network model. The Neural network model is trained to learn the password patterns which reduces the computation speed and increases the performance with reduced time complexity.Feed forward neural network,Percepstron network, Recurrent network are analysed and the results are discussed.

Index Terms—Authentication, Neural Network,Mobile Adhoc Network,Feed Forward Neural Network Back Propagation

Introduction

Mobile adhoc network is deployed instantly in case of disaster recovery models,conferences, online learning, campus based applications,military applications and for outdoor applications.Some of the applications do not need any authentication schemes.But the necessity of authentication is essential for most of the applications.some of the network protocols have no authentication schemes.Due to the lack of infrastructure and central authority, such systems with no authentication schemes may face severe security threats.Implementing the security in Manets is not a easier challenge.For authentication purposes, several schemes have been followed based on key management and cryptographic techniques.Shared session keys,pairwise keys,public key cryptography,hashing,digital signatures are used for authentication purposes.Due to the resources limitation and mobility features, light weight fast and efficient security solutions are required.The authentication schemes also depend on computational requirements and storage complexity. Katrin Hoepfer and Guang Gong[1] in their work designed new protocol such as 3-stage protocol and 2-stage protocol.The 3-stage protocol includes three phases such as pre-authentication,authentication and session key establishment. Tomasz Ciszkowski Zbigniew Kotulski [2] proposed new Anonymous authentication protocol in ad hoc networks .It consists of two complementary modules by establishing and maintaining bidirectional routes form source to the destination and by monitoring activity of nodes being along the existing or discovering path and evaluate their reputation.Anonymity based security is another way of ensuring security in mobile adhoc networks. Active attacks and passive attacks in mobile adhoc networks are surveyed widely in previous literatures. Passive attacks may also include overhearing and active attacks tries to focus on data and object controls.The attacks may be classified in terms of physical layer,mac layer, network layer,Transport layer and application layer. By considering all these factors, it is obvious that the lack of security is reflected from the physical layer to higher levels. Malicious interruption nodes in wireless mobile ad-hoc networks are a greater threat concerning security as well as anonymity of exchanged information.Since Authentication is an initial step for a node to participate, it is focused.The authentication schemes rely on trusted third party servers or called certificate authorities.Kerberos,x.509 standard are some of the popular authentication schemes. Cluster based authentication schemes, Trust based authentication schemes uses public key cryptography schemes. Identity based encryption schemes which uses email address as key are used.The encryption and decryption are performed with a threshold timer.There are different authentication schemes performed in Manet.In this work, authentication scheme is performed using Neural Network techniques such as Feed forward Backpropagation network,Percepstron network and Recurrent Network.The performance is analysed with different kinds of encrypted passwordds.In the remaining sections the Neural network methodology is discussed and the Neural network models designed for the authentication in Mobile adhoc network is discussed.

A. Neural Network Methodology

Artificial Neural Network can compute any models of thinking and conscience.It is used for mapping problems that concern manipulation of symbols and memory.It is a natural fault tolerant system which can be

applied to decision systems. Artificial Neural network consist of many nodes which are known as processing units similar to neurons in the brain. The signals are transmitted via connection links. The input unit is connected via hidden layer. The behavior of the output unit depends on the weight associated with the connecting neurons in the hidden layer and the output layer. In general, the artificial Neural Network is characterized by,

1. Architecture – Neurons.
2. Determining weights on the connections.
3. Activation function

Figure 1. represents the general architecture of Neural Network. There are many architecture for neural networks such as single layer feed forward, multilayer feed forward, fully recurrent, competitive network and so on. Artificial neural network has many learning rule such as:

Table 1. Types of Learning Rule

S.No	Learning Rule
1.	Hebbian
2.	Perceptron
3.	Widrow Holf or Delta
4.	Competitive
5.	Outstar
6.	Boltzmann
7.	Memory based.

Figure.1. Neural Network architecture

The main capability of Artificial Neural Network is to learn. Learning or training is a process by means of which a neural network adapts itself to a stimulus by making proper parameter adjustments resulting in the production of desired response. The Learning can be classified as:

Table 2. Types of Learning

S.No	Types of Learning
1.	Supervised
2.	Unsupervised
3.	Reinforcement

In supervised learning, the Neural network is trained according to the desired output. If there exists a difference in output, an error signal is generated. This error signal is used for the adjustments of weights. The Neural network is trained until the actual output matches. In the network, a supervisor is required for error minimization. The

types of supervised learning are listed in Table[3]. The second major Learning Paradigm is unsupervised Learning. In this types of network, the desired output is not indicated. But the unsupervised learning can judge, how similar a new input pattern matches with the typical pattern already explored. It is also used for decision making system. The types of unsupervised learning are listed in Table 4.

Table 3. Types of supervised Learning

S.No	Types of supervised learning
1.	Perceptron
2.	Adaline
3.	Multiple Adaptive Linear
4.	Backpropogation
5.	Radial basis
6.	Time delay
7.	Functional link
8.	Tree Neural
9.	Wavelet Neural

Table 4. Types of Unsupervised Learning

S.No	Types of Unsupervised learning
1.	Fixed weight competitive nets
2.	Kohonen self organizaing feature maps
3.	Learning vector quantization
4.	Counter propogation networks
5.	Adaptive Resonance theory network

Reinforcement Learning :

It is similar to supervised Learning. But if the correct target value is not known ,critic information is given. This type of learning is called reinforcement learning.

II. PROPOSED WORK

A. System design

This paper proposes a new methodology for password authentication using neural networks. Since the neural networks reduces computation overhead, an attempt has been made to train the neural networks with the encrypted password. For a mobile Adhoc network model, a central authority node is chosen as the Zone head node. The zone head is trained with a set of authentication codewords with neural network. The participation nodes are authenticated with the username and password. If the password matches with the trained password, the nodes are allowed for further participation. This methodology will reduce the participation of the malicious node from participating in the network. The neural network model will be easier for training and it reduces the computational complexity when compared with other algorithms. Modifications in the input dataset will be easier and huge datasets can be given as input depending on the applications and high security requirements of Manets. Neural Network methodology has different models and learning as discussed in the previous section. For the authentication in Manets, Feed Forward back propogation neural network with different activation functions, Recurrent network and Perceptron network are analysed. The initial system design for the model is designed as:

Figure 2. System design

B. Network model

An undirected graph $G(V, E)$ denotes the Mobile adhoc network ‘n’ number of nodes $N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_n\}$. connect If the nodes are located within the transmission range of each other, then $N(n_i)$ represents the set of neighborhood nodes located within the transmission range of node n_i . Let v_i be the Zone Head which acts as an central administrator. The user id is (ID_r) and password (PW_r) . The ID and Password is encrypted and the encrypted data is converted into binary code value to feed as input to the neural network. The following table represents the sample list of encrypted passwords.

Table 5. List of Encrypted Passwords

S.No	Encrypted Passwords
1.	0000363AF51392C9C15E5B93924DBF720F30FF85
2.	000039E7065D98862742CF12544B10C1C262519A
3.	0000BA996ED92A2EEA1DDD7AD886EA64295C0F51
4.	0000C1BDAB3A615C3B636084CC33171482948D5A
5.	0000F4B5EB4502F10ADC426238F2DF8778399E06

The binary value for the following Encrypted password generated is :

0000363AF51392C9C15E5B93924DBF720F30FF85
 00110000 00110000 00110000 00110000 00110011 00110110 00110011 01000001 01000110 00110101
 00110001 00110011 00111001 00110010 01000011 00111001 01000011 00110001 00110101 01000101
 00110101 01000010 00111001 00110011 00111001 00110010 00110100 01000100 01000010 01000110

00110111 00110010 00110000 01000110 00110011 00110000 01000110 01000110 00111000 00110101
00001101 00001010

The binary code value is fed as input to the Neural Network.

C. Backpropagation Neural Network :

It is a systematic method for training multilayer Artificial Neural Network. It uses gradient descent based delta learning rule, commonly known as back propagation of errors. Being a gradient descent method, it minimizes the total squared error of the output. The inputs are sent to the Backpropagation network and the output obtained from the net could be either binary(0,1) or bipolar (-1,+1).

The training algorithm is :

$$\text{Let } x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots \dots \dots x_i, \dots \dots x_n)$$

be the encrypted password.

$$\text{Let } y = (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, \dots \dots \dots y_i, \dots \dots y_n)$$

Be the target output vector.

- Let α = learning parameter
- x_i = input unit i.
- ϑ_{0j} = Bias on the j^{th} Hidden unit
- ω_{0k} = bias on the k^{th} Output unit
- z_j = hidden unit j.

The net input to z_j is

$$z_{inj} = \vartheta_{0j} + \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i v_{ij}) \text{ and the output is}$$

$$z_j = f(z_{inj})$$

$$y_k = \text{Output unit } k$$

The net input to y_k is

$$y_{ink} = \omega_{0k} + \sum_{j=1}^p (z_j \omega_{jk})$$

And the output is

$$y_k = f(y_{ink})$$

δ_k = Error correction weight adjustment for w_{jk}

δ_j = Error correction weight adjustment for v_{ij}

The range of α is from 10^{-3} to 10 for back propagation.

Sigmoidal Function :

The sigmoidal function reduces the computational burden during training.

Logistic Sigmoid Function :

It is also termed as Logistic sigmoid or unipolar sigmoid function. It can be defined as :

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\lambda x}}$$

Where λ is the steepness parameter and the range of the sigmoid function is from 0 to 1.

Hyperbolic Tangent Function :

$$h(x) = \frac{1-e^{-2x}}{1+e^{-2x}}$$

The architecture of artificial neural network with a training pattern of 8 input values is as :

Figure 3 .ANN model

D. Perceptron Network

Perceptron Network has 3 units namely sensory unit(input),assoicator and response unit(output unit).The activation function is 1,0 or -1.The output of the perceptron network is given by

$$y = f(y_{in})$$

The activation function is

$$y = f(y_{in}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y_{in} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } -\theta \leq y_{in} \leq \theta \\ -1 & \text{if } y_{in} < -\theta \end{cases}$$

The response of the output unit is

$$y_{in} = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i w_i)$$

E. Recurrent network

The Hopfield network is an auto associative fully interconnected single layer feedback network.[3].If it operates in discrete fashion, then its architecture is called Recuurent network.This network has no self connections.In this network,only one unit will update its activation.

Training Algorithm :

- 1.Initialize the weights to store patterns.
- 2.When the activation function is not converged, then perform steps 2-8.
- 3.The initial activations are set
- 4.The net input of the network is

$$y_{ini} = x_i + \sum_j (y_j w_{ji})$$

- 5.Apply the activations in the net input to calculate the output

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y_{ini} > \theta_i \\ y_i & \text{if } y_{ini} = \theta_i \\ 0 & \text{if } y_{ini} < \theta_i \end{cases}$$

Where θ_i is the threshold and is normally taken as zero.

- 6.The activation vectors are updated by transmitting the output y_i to all other units.

The data is tested with the three networks using Matlab simulink tool and the outputs are Obtained.Feed forward Backpropogation network mean squared error plot with sigmoid function is as follows:

Figure 4 . Performance using Feed Forward Back propagation Network with sigmoid Activation Function

Full set of input samples is passed to the neural network to compute the Least squared error function. Each such pass is referred as pass. The mean squared error is the sum of the squared differences between the desired output and the actual output of the output neurons averaged over all training exemplars. [4] A small value close to zero indicates that the network has learned well and is suited for the classification problem. [4]. The supported training function is TrainLm which represents the Levenberg –Marquardt back propagation. The network is trained with Tangent function and the result is :

Figure 5. Performance using Feed Forward Back propagation Network with Tangent Activation Function

Figure 6 .Performance using Perceptron network

Figure 7. Performance using Recurrent Network

The best validation performance and the epoch is tabulated for different kinds of networks as follows :

S.No	Network	Performance	Epoch
1.	Feed forward Backpropagation (TANSIG)	0.1808	Epoch 2
2.	Feed forward Backpropagation (LOGSIG)	0.25397	Epoch 0
3.	Recurrent	0.0032571	Epoch 0
4.	Perceptron	0.4375	Epoch 0

CONCLUSION

Neural network finds its application in every area of research including image processing and mining applications. Many network authentication algorithms and cryptographic algorithms requires more space and time complexity. The neural network models will reduce the computational problems and it will be best suited for training and recognizing the patterns. Since authentication in Mobile adhoc network is a very important factor, an approach to use the neural network methodology is analysed in this work and implemented. It shows that the password learning can be used efficiently using different types of networks in Neural network methodology.

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